

Role of Antioxidants in Hypoxia-Induced Learning and Memory Deficit

Entesar Yaseen Abdo Qaid¹⁾, Rahimah Zakaria¹⁾, Shaída Fariza Sulaiman²⁾,
Nurul Aiman Mohd Yusof³⁾, Nazlahshaniza Shafin¹⁾, Zahiruddin Othman⁴⁾,
Asma Hayati Ahmad¹⁾, Badriya Al-Rahbi⁵⁾

ABSTRACT

Background: Search for natural antioxidants to ameliorate hypoxia-induced cognitive dysfunctions has attracted great interest in recent years.

Objective: This paper aimed to review published original articles on the efficacy of natural antioxidant compounds that could protect neuronal morphology and cognitive function following hypoxia exposure.

Method: A narrative literature review was undertaken. This review provides evidence from animal studies which highlights common natural antioxidants that have been used in adult animal experiments to ameliorate the cognitive impairment caused by environmental hypoxia.

Conclusion: Natural antioxidant compounds show promise of conferring neuroprotection and preserving cognitive function following hypoxia exposure and warrants further exploration.

KEY WORDS

hypoxia, oxidative stress, antioxidant, memory, learning

INTRODUCTION

Hypoxia is either absolute or relative lack of oxygen in organs, tissues, or cells. Absolute hypoxia can be due to a reduced supply of oxygen. The causes include low oxygen in inspired air, insufficient blood vessel network, defective blood vessel, and anemia. Relative hypoxia can be due to increased consumption of oxygen relative to its supply caused by sudden high cell proliferation or metabolic rate.

Although the whole brain is susceptible to hypoxia, hippocampus in particular is reported to be severely affected^{1,2)}. The hippocampus plays crucial roles in encoding and consolidating memory^{3,4)}. Many studies show that hypoxic injury to the brain especially to the hippocampus, triggers memory loss and causes learning and memory deficits^{5,6)}.

intermittent or continuous low oxygen environment. For *in vivo* studies, continuous hypoxia rat model is used to study the effect of acute mountain sickness (AMS), diseases/conditions associated with low oxygen supply to the brain such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and brain encephalopathies, medication and drugs, concussion, or changes in air quality, for example in a nuclear power plant. Intermittent hypoxia rat model, on the other hand, is commonly used to study the effects of obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA). Chemical inductions such as exposure to carbon monoxide (CO), cobalt (II) chloride hexahydrate (CoCl) and sodium nitrite are commonly used to establish hypoxia environment for *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies⁷⁻⁹⁾. The surgical (invasive) method of hypoxia induction such as bilateral occlusion of the common carotid arteries¹⁰⁾, can be used singly or in combination with exposure to a low oxygen environment.

HYPOXIA INDUCTION

Hypoxia can be induced by surgical or nonsurgical methods. One of the nonsurgical methods of hypoxia induction is exposure to either

DEFINITION OF ANTIOXIDANT

An antioxidant is defined as any substance that, when present at low concentrations compared to that of an oxidizable substrate, significantly

Received on February 25, 2019 and accepted on June 3, 2019

1) Department of Physiology, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
16150 Kubang Kerian, Malaysia

2) School of Biological Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
11800 Penang, Malaysia

3) Department of Anatomy, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
16150 Kubang Kerian, Malaysia

4) Department of Psychiatry, School of Medical Sciences, Universiti Sains Malaysia
16150 Kubang Kerian, Malaysia

5) Oman College of Health Sciences, Ministry of Health
Muscat, Oman

Correspondence to: Asma Hayati Ahmad
(e-mail: asmakck@usm.my)

delays or inhibits oxidation of that substrate¹¹). The antioxidant can also be defined as any substance that delays, prevents or removes oxidative damage to a target molecule¹²). Khlebnikov *et al.*¹³), however, defined antioxidant as any substance that directly scavenges reactive oxygen species (ROS) or indirectly acts to up-regulate antioxidant defenses or inhibit ROS production. Apart from the above properties, an antioxidant may have an ability to convert free radical to a new stable radical through intramolecular hydrogen bonding on further oxidation¹⁴).

TYPES OF ANTIOXIDANT

There are two types of antioxidant; natural and synthetic. Natural antioxidants can be obtained through diet in the form of fruits, spices, vegetables, etc.¹⁵). They are commonly studied because of several reasons. Firstly, controversies on the safety and carcinogenic effects of synthetic antioxidants have been reported. For example, butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA), widely used as antioxidants in the food industry, may be responsible for liver damage and carcinogenesis^{16,17}). Secondly, the beneficial effects of a compound may not arise from a single antioxidant. For example, many honey components, particularly the flavonoids and phenolic acids, have been shown to contribute significantly to the antioxidant capacity. However, when separated from honey and tested in *in vitro* systems, they produce only a portion of the total antioxidant activity of honey. These results suggest that several antioxidants may act synergistically in honey¹⁸). Research for non-toxic natural antioxidants and synergistic interactions of multi-component herbal preparations as well as their interactions with pharmaceutical drugs has also attracted great interest in recent years^{19,20}).

EFFECTS OF ANTIOXIDANTS ON LEARNING AND MEMORY OF ADULT ANIMAL EXPOSED TO HYPOXIC ENVIRONMENT

Bacopa monnieri

Bacopa monnieri (BM), also known as brahmi, water hyssop, *Bacopa somnifera*, and *Herpestis monnieri*, is a creeping perennial with small oblong leaves and purple flowers found in warm wetlands, and native to Australia and India. Commonly found as a weed in rice fields, BM grows throughout East Asia and the United States²¹).

Hota *et al.*²²) investigated the therapeutic potential of a bacoside-rich leaf extract of BM in improving memory functions in male Sprague Dawley rats in hypobaric conditions. The rats learning ability was evaluated along with memory retrieval following exposure to hypobaric conditions simulating an altitude of 25,000 ft. for different durations. They found significant decline in oxidative stress as evidenced by decreased protein oxidation and lipid peroxidation along with augmented antioxidant status in the bacoside-administered animals on exposure to hypobaric hypoxia. This finding has been attributed to the antioxidative role of bacosides²³).

Bacoside supplementation has also been reported to decrease lipid peroxidation and necrotic alteration in the cornu ammonis (CA1) region of hippocampus in conditions of aluminum-induced oxidative stress²⁴). Besides that, it has also been reported to exert a protective effect on DNA cleavage and exhibit free radical scavenging activity in hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) UV-photolysis model of oxidative stress²⁵). The exhibited antioxidant property of bacosides may in part be due to the existence of a similar free radical scavenging mechanism. In addition, decreased glutamate synthesis and release in bacosides-treated hypoxic animals may also considerably contribute to their augmented antioxidant status in comparison with untreated animals. This is because glutamate and cysteine which are the precursors for glutathione synthesis share the same transporter for their cellular uptake. Excess glutamate released in hypobaric conditions therefore competitively inhibits cysteine uptake thus resulting in attenuated glutathione synthesis and depletion of the antioxidant status²⁵). The augmented glutamatergic transmission provided by bacosides in hypobaric conditions is more likely to be due to its antioxidant properties. Hypobaric hypoxia per se increases NR1 expression (a subunit of N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors), thereby pointing towards overstimulation of the NMDA receptors.

Although there is increase in cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP)-responsive element binding protein (CREB) phosphorylation in hypoxia as observed from the total CREB-phospho CREB ratio, a decrease in total CREB is observed when compared with the normoxic and bacoside administered groups, thus decreasing its availability for phosphorylation. The decreased CREB expression in hypobaric hypoxia is probably due to excitotoxic neuronal loss and free radical-mediated protein degradation as indicated by increased protein carbonyls. Bacoside administration decreases the oxidative stress induced by hypobaric exposure thus preventing CREB degradation and augmenting memory functions in hypobaric hypoxia. On the other hand, administration of bacosides to normoxic animals increases CREB phosphorylation thus facilitating memory acquisition and retrieval²²).

Withania somnifera

Withania somnifera (WS) is commonly known as Ashwagandha, Indian ginseng, or Winter Cherry²⁶). The plant grows in the form of shrub with a lot of branching. Its height reaches to around 150 cm and the leaves are up to 10 cm long. The flowers are greenish or lurid yellow while fruits/berries when mature are orange colored. Its seeds are sown mostly during the month of June or July^{27,28}). It is found throughout the drier parts of India, Baluchistan, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Sri Lanka, Congo, South Africa, Egypt, Morocco and Jordan²⁹).

The neuroprotective effect of WS root extract, supplemented to male Sprague Dawley rats during a period of 21 days' pre-exposure and 7 days' exposure to a simulated altitude of 25,000 ft., has been shown to improve hippocampal neurodegeneration and hypobaric hypoxia-mediated memory impairment. The results of the study show reduced nitric oxide (NO), corticosterone and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in the hippocampal region. The underlying mechanism of WS root extract include: (i) increased acetylcholine levels with upregulation of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), (ii) modulation of NO-cyclooxygenase-prostaglandin signalling that inhibits the synthesis and release of corticosterone, (iii) direct scavenging of oxidative free radicals generated during hypoxic exposure via its contents of flavonoid and other potent antioxidants, and (4) decreased expression of pro-apoptotic protein Bax and upregulation of Bcl-2 expression³⁰).

Swertia Species

The plant species of genus *Swertia* are diverse and the large genus populated with 170 species^{31,32}) is distributed in the mountainous region of tropical Asia, Europe, America and Africa at an altitude of 1200-3600 m. Most of the *Swertia* species are found in the Himalayan regions^{33,34}). *Swertia* species are known to contain various active components including antioxidant xanthenes, seco-irrioid glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolics^{31,33,35}).

A recent study by Kaushal and colleagues³⁶) investigated the neuro-modulatory potential of *S. chirata* and *S. cordata* during hypoxia-induced neuronal damage in Wistar rats. The rats were placed inside a custom-made hypoxia chamber (10% O₂) for 3 days and treated with 100 mg/kg *S. chirata* and *S. cordata* extract for 7 days before being subjected to motor function (Rotarod test) and memory function (active and passive avoidance tests) assessments. Rats exposed to hypoxia demonstrated significantly ($p < 0.001$) lower latency to enter the dark chamber during retention trials and higher transfer latency to enter the safer region of the apparatus, thereby suggesting that the animals were not able to remember the foot shock they received in the dark chamber during learning trials and were not able to associate between auditory cues and foot shock. Hypoxic rats receiving extract treatment significantly improved their learning and memory performance when compared to their untreated counterparts. Three days of hypoxia, however, did not impair muscle coordination and animals had normal muscular activity. The hydroalcoholic extracts of *S. chirata* and *S. cordata* were found to efficiently improve hypoxia-mediated memory dysfunction. This effect was attributed to their antioxidant properties to reduce mitochondrial ROS generation and lipid peroxidation, as well as to increase catalase activity and glutathione levels in rats' hippocampi.

Acetyl-L-carnitine

Acetyl-L-carnitine (ALCAR), an acetylated form of L-carnitine, is produced in the body, but can also be consumed as a dietary supplement. It is broken down in the blood by plasma esterase to carnitines which is then transported into the mitochondria for breakdown, and is involved in energy metabolism and mitochondrial protection. The ALCAR is often used as a brain booster due to its ability to support the

neurons by increasing mitochondrial capacity thereby increasing alertness. Research shows immense therapeutic potential of ALCAR for the treatment of ischemia, stroke, and other neurodegenerative disorders associated with hypoxic stress and excitotoxicity^{37,38}.

The neuroprotective effect of ALCAR that ameliorates hypoxia-induced hippocampal neurodegeneration and memory impairment has been observed when supplemented in a dose of 75 mg/kg to male rats with neurotoxicity and hypobaric hypoxia-induced memory impairment. The rats were kept in an environment simulating altitude equivalent to 6100 m (21,000 ft.) for 3 days³⁹. The antioxidant and anti-apoptotic activities of this compound were considered important mechanisms of action. ALCAR has been found to decrease free radical production, lipid peroxidation, and lactate dehydrogenase (LD) activity, and augments antioxidant capacity by increasing the ratio of reduced to oxidized glutathione (GSH/GSSH), and increasing the levels of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione reductase (GR). Subsequently, this results in deactivation of the apoptotic pathway via downregulation of cytochrome c release, caspase-3 level, and Bcl-2 expression. In addition, it upregulates nerve growth factor (NGF) which consequently activates extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) phosphorylation pathway, leading to enhancement of cholinergic transmission, and stabilization of mitochondrial membrane that support neuronal function⁴⁰⁻⁴².

Calcium channel blocker

Isradipine, a selective L-type calcium channel blocker, belongs to the family of 1,4-dihydropyridines (DHPs). The neuroprotective effect of isradipine in rat and mouse models of cerebral ischemia and Parkinson's disease has been reported^{43,44}.

Calcium overload in brain tissue, particularly hippocampus, plays a major role in the pathogenesis of hypobaric hypoxia-induced memory impairment^{21,45,46}. The neuroprotective effect of isradipine, at a dose of 2.5 mg/kg, has been observed in male rats subjected to hypobaric hypoxia simulating an altitude of 25,000 ft. for different durations. The enhancement of CA1 region morphology and cognitive function were attributed to antioxidant capacity and calcium channel blocking activity of isradipine. The findings of this study include deactivation of L-type calcium channels, low level of calcium-dependent enzymes such as xanthine oxidases, cytosolic phospholipase A2, monoamine oxidases, and cyclooxygenase (COX-2), and decrease in free radical production, cytochrome c activation and expression of apoptotic markers involving calpain and caspase-3⁴⁵. The underlying mechanism of calcium channel blockers is inhibition of all enzymes responsible for oxidative stress pathway activation such as xanthine oxidases, cytosolic phospholipase A2, monoamine oxidases, and COX-2, with subsequent decrease in free radicals production and neuronal damage.

Cobalt chloride

Cobalt is an element mainly obtained as a by-product of nickel and copper mining, and is separated from the ores (mainly cobaltite, erythrite, glaucodot, and skutterudite) using a variety of processes. Its compounds include several oxides such as blue cobalt (II) chloride (CoCl₂), green cobalt (II) bromide (CoBr₂), and blue-black cobalt (II) iodide (CoI₂). The main application of cobalt is in its metal form as cobalt-based batteries, pigments, and alloys, whereas its chemical application is mainly as cobalt chloride (CoCl₂). Its cognitive enhancer role in a rat model of perinatal hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy has been reported⁴⁷.

Antioxidant effect of cobalt chloride, at a dose of 50 mg/kg, ameliorates oxidative stress in brain tissue of rats exposed to hypobaric hypoxia at a simulated altitude equivalent to 7619 m (26,272 ft.) for 48 hr has been observed. This antioxidant effect seen was decreased reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) generation, lipid peroxidation and protein oxidation, as well as increased superoxide dismutase (SOD), GPx, and glutathione-S-transferase (GST) levels. Another effect was the maintenance of GSH/GSSH ratio to control level via activation of hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α (HIF-1 α) signaling mechanisms that maintain higher cellular heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1) and metallothionein (MT) II and III which offers higher neuroprotection⁴⁸. The effect of this compound on cognitive function was not evaluated in this study. However, since oxidative stress plays a critical role in the pathogenesis of memory impairment during hypoxia, it is speculated that the antioxidant activity of this compound may improve hypoxia-induced cognitive dysfunction.

N-acetylcysteine

N-acetylcysteine (NAC), also known as acetylcysteine or N-acetyl-L-cysteine, is a specially modified form of the dietary amino acid cysteine, the building blocks of body proteins. It is an essential source of sulfhydryl (SH) groups, and is transformed in the body into metabolites capable of stimulating glutathione synthesis, enhancing detoxification, and working directly as free radical scavengers⁴⁹. Its cognitive-enhancing effects have been reported in neurologic diseases that induce memory impairment associated with decreased GSH and increased oxidative stress products, such as amyloid β -peptide-induced learning and memory deficits and diabetic neuropathy⁵⁰⁻⁵².

Jayalakshmi *et al.*⁵³ showed improvement of rat's spatial working and reference memory functions in male rats exposed to hypobaric hypoxia equivalent to an altitude of 6100 m (21,000 ft.) for 3 days following NAC supplementation at a daily dose of 750 mg/kg. The study findings included elevation of GSH, GPx, and GR levels, reduction in free radical production and malondialdehyde (MDA) level, and improvement of spatial working and reference memory. The neuroprotective effect of this compound is attributed to its antioxidant properties as evidenced by improvement of oxidative stress status of hippocampal cell culture in rats exposed to hypobaric hypoxia and treated with NAC compared to untreated group.

Naringenine

Naringenine (NGEN), a bioflavonoid, is a natural chemical compound extracted from the inner peel of grape fruit and other citrus fruits. It is also available as a supplement, usually as part of a comprehensive formula with other bioflavonoids such as curcumin and quercetin. Its neuroprotective effect, acting via deactivation of oxidative stress and inflammatory pathways, is seen in various neurologic diseases such as stroke and diabetic encephalopathy^{54,55}.

NGEN supplementation (50 mg/kg) daily for 21 days to a rat model of cerebral ischemic/reperfusion injury has been shown to exert neuroprotective effects. These effects are observed as upregulation of antioxidant status and reduction of infarct size, NO, myeloperoxidase, and cytokines levels, along with functional recovery close to the baseline. In addition, it also limits glial cells activation and downregulates nuclear factor kappa beta (NF- κ B) and their target expression⁵⁵.

The synergistic action of NGEN with other nutrients, including quercetin (QR), augments the bioavailability and therefore maximizes the health benefits of these compounds. The single or combined administration of NGEN and quercetin has been shown to provide antioxidant neuroprotective effects in neurologic diseases-induced oxidative stress and cognitive dysfunction^{55,56}.

Enhancement of hypobaric hypoxia-induced neuronal damage and behavioural impairment (alterations in fore limb usage and motor impairments) have been observed following combined administration of NGEN and QR, in a dose of 10 mg/kg each, to mice subjected to normobaric hypoxia equivalent to 8% O₂ for 12 hr for one day and for fifteen consecutive days⁵⁷. The results of this study showed that the acute and chronic hypoxic group supplemented by NGEN and QR had more decreases in reactive oxygen species production, expression of HIF-1 α , vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), active caspase-3 and ubiquitin levels; less degenerated neurons in hippocampus, cortex and striatum; and more increases in GSH level and rearing behaviour, compared to the hypoxic mice that did not receive any supplementation. The antioxidant activities of both compounds play important roles in the improvement of neuronal morphology and increase in rearing behaviour in this study.

Quercetin

Quercetin (QR), also a bioflavonoid, is a natural chemical compound extracted from fruits and vegetables, such as red wine, onions, green tea, apples and berries. Studies show that QR plays an important role in amelioration of memory function in neurologic diseases associated with oxidative stress and cognitive impairment^{58,59}.

The neuroprotective effect of QR following exposure to hypoxia is demonstrated in a study by Patir *et al.*⁶⁰. Pretreatment with oral QR, in a dose of 50 mg/kg body weight, improved cerebral edema and inflammation in male Sprague-Dawley rats subjected to hypobaric hypoxia equivalent to an altitude of 25,000 ft. for 24 hr. The findings included a decrease in free radical generation and MDA level, increase in antioxidant enzyme levels involving GSH, GPx and SOD, and down-regulation of NF κ B activity in QR treated group.

The cognitive-enhancing effect of QR, by improving hippocampal

neurodegeneration and memory impairment-induced hypobaric hypoxia has also been reported⁶¹). Using a similar regime of hypobaric hypoxia induction and QUR supplementation dose as Patir *et al.*⁶⁰, the biochemical and histological findings showed elevated antioxidant enzymes levels with consequent reduced lipid peroxidation in the hippocampus, reduced caspase-3 expression, decreased number of pyknotic and degenerated neurons in the hippocampus; these along with enhancement of spatial memory function in QUR-treated group.

Additional beneficial effects of QUR have been evidenced in another study on male Wistar rats exposed to hypobaric hypoxia simulating an altitude of 5000 m (17,000 ft.) for 23 hours per day. Supplementation with QUR, in doses of 5, 10, and 20 mg/kg for 5 days, has been shown to increase antioxidant enzymes levels including SOD, catalase (CAT), and GPx; reduce MDA serum levels; elevate the decline in pH, PO₂, SpO₂, PCO₂ as well as Na⁺, HCO₃⁻, and Cl⁻ levels in arterial blood; and increase the levels and activities of NO and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) along with reducing K⁺ concentrations in serum⁶². The underlying mechanism may be attributed to antioxidant properties of QUR that augment antioxidant enzymes levels/activities and decrease free radical and MDA levels that subsequently equilibrate the arterial blood gases and electrolytes levels, preserve neuronal structure and improve memory function.

Zinc chelators

A zinc chelating agent known as calcium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (Ca₂EDTA) is used to sequester a variety of polyvalent cations such as zinc that accumulates in brain tissue, particularly hippocampus, during hypoxia exposure. The excess level of zinc in neuronal tissue has been associated with oxidative stress and neuronal loss⁶³ and the role of zinc chelators to improve neuronal function has been shown in many neurologic diseases associated with oxidative stress and zinc accumulation^{64,65}.

The neuroprotective effect of Ca₂EDTA, at a dose of 1.25 mM/kg, in ameliorating spatial working and associative memory deficits in male rats exposed to hypobaric hypoxia, equivalent to an altitude of 25,000 ft. for 6 hr a day for 3 days, has been evidenced. Its antiinflammatory, antioxidant and antiapoptotic role via stabilization of low gene expression of pro-inflammatory markers such as iNOS, MT-3, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α) consequent to destabilization effect on HIF-1 α , attenuation of superoxide generation via reduction of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen (NADPH) oxidase activity, together with reduction of MDA and NO levels, and significant reduction of caspase-3 activity, have been suggested as the underlying mechanisms⁶⁶. In addition, the zinc chelator upregulates the activity of acetylcholinesterase and expression of choline acetyl-transferase and muscarinic receptor 1 and 4 following hypobaric hypoxia exposure via chelation of intracellular free chelatable zinc in the hippocampal CA3 pyramidal neurons that induces neuronal loss and memory impairment in hypobaric hypoxic condition⁶³.

CONCLUSION

Disturbance of cognitive function following normobaric or hypobaric hypoxia exposure represents a serious neurologic issue. Natural antioxidant compounds show promise of conferring neuroprotection and preserving cognitive function following hypoxia exposure and warrants further exploration. This review provides evidence from animal studies which may be applied to clinical situations in which exposure to hypoxia potentially disturbs neuronal morphology and cognitive functioning. Further studies should be conducted to evaluate the molecular mechanism(s) of action of these compounds.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author(s) disclose receipt of the following financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article: This research received funding from USM Short-term Grant (304/PPSP/61313086).

REFERENCES

1) Brierley J. Experimental hypoxic brain damage. *J Clin Pathol Suppl (R Coll Pathol)*

- 1977; 11: 181.
- 2) Reed L, Marsden P, Lasserson D, Sheldon N, Lewis P, Stanhope N, Guinan E, Kopelman, M. FDG-PET analysis and findings in amnesia resulting from hypoxia. *Memory* 1999; 7(5-6): 599-614.
- 3) Morris R, Garrud P, Rawlins JN, O'Keefe J. Place navigation impaired in rats with hippocampal lesions. *Nature* 1982; 297(5868): 681-683.
- 4) Squire LR. Memory and the hippocampus: a synthesis from findings with rats, monkeys, and humans. *Psychol Rev* 1992; 99(2): 195.
- 5) Shukitt-Hale B, Stillman MJ, Lieberman HR. Tyrosine administration prevents hypoxia-induced decrements in learning and memory. *Physiol Behav* 1996; 59(4): 867-871.
- 6) Balduini W, De Angelis V, Mazzoni E, Cimino M. Long-lasting behavioral alterations following a hypoxic/ischemic brain injury in neonatal rats. *Brain Res* 2000; 859(2): 318-325.
- 7) Wu D, Yotnda P. Induction and testing of hypoxia in cell culture. *JoVE* 2011; 54: 2899. doi:10.3791/2899.
- 8) Rani A, Prasad S. A special extract of bacopa monnieri (CDRI-08)-restored memory in coel2-hypoxia mimetic mice is associated with upregulation of Fmr-1 gene expression in hippocampus. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med* 2015; 2015: 347978. Published online 2015 Aug 27. doi:10.1155/2015/347978.
- 9) Lu X, Lai Z, Du MJ. Protection of Salvia Miltiorrhiza against Acute Sodium Nitrite Poisoning in Mice. *International Medical Journal* 2016; 23(2): 145-147
- 10) Saxena AK, Phyu HP, Al-Ani IM, Oothuman P. Improved spatial learning and memory performance following Tualang honey treatment during cerebral hypoperfusion-induced neurodegeneration. *J Transl Sci* 2016; 2(5): 264-271.
- 11) Halliwell B, Gutteridge JM. The definition and measurement of antioxidants in biological systems. *Free Radic Biol Med* 1995; 18(1): 125-126.
- 12) Halliwell B. Oxidative stress and cancer: have we moved forward? *Biochem J* 2007; 401(1): 1-11.
- 13) Khlebnikov AI, Schepetkin IA, Domina NG, Kirpotina LN, Quinn MT. Improved quantitative structure-activity relationship models to predict antioxidant activity of flavonoids in chemical, enzymatic, and cellular systems. *Bioorganic Med Chem* 2007; 15(4): 1749-1770.
- 14) Halliwell B, Gutteridge JM. Role of free radicals and catalytic metal ions in human disease: an overview. *Methods Enzymol* 1990; 186: 1-85.
- 15) Ayoub Z, Mehta A. Medicinal plants as potential source of antioxidant agents: a review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res* 2018; 11(6): 50-56.
- 16) Grice H. Safety evaluation of butylated hydroxyanisole from the perspective of effects on forestomach and oesophageal squamous epithelium. *Food Chem Toxicol* 1988; 26(8): 717-723.
- 17) Murphy P, Myers D, Davies M, Webster N, Jones J. The antioxidant potential of propofol (2, 6-diisopropylphenol). *BJA* 1992; 68(6): 613-618.
- 18) Gheldof N, Engeseth NJ. Antioxidant capacity of honeys from various floral sources based on the determination of oxygen radical absorbance capacity and inhibition of in vitro lipoprotein oxidation in human serum samples. *J Agric Food Chem* 2002; 50(10): 3050-3055.
- 19) Liu X, Wang D, Zhao R, Dong X, Hu Y, Liu P. Synergistic Neuroprotective Effects of Two Herbal Ingredients via CREB-Dependent Pathway. *Front Pharmacol* 2016; 7: 337. doi:10.3389/fphar.2016.00337.
- 20) Zhou X, Seto SW, Chang D, Kiat H, Razmovski-Naumovski V, Chan K, Bensoussan A. Synergistic Effects of Chinese Herbal Medicine: A Comprehensive Review of Methodology and Current Research. *Front Pharmacol* 2016; 7: 201. <http://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2016.00201>.
- 21) Aguiar S, Borowski T. Neuropharmacological review of the nootropic herb Bacopa monnieri. *Rejuvenation Res* 2013; 16(4): 313-326.
- 22) Hota SK, Barhwal K, Baitharu I, Prasad D, Singh SB, Ilavazhagan G. Bacopa monnieri leaf extract ameliorates hypobaric hypoxia induced spatial memory impairment. *Neurobiol Dis* 2009; 34(1): 23-39.
- 23) Russo A, Izzo AA, Borrelli F, Renis M, Vanella A. Free radical scavenging capacity and protective effect of Bacopa monnieri L. on DNA damage. *Phytother Res* 2003; 17(8): 870-875.
- 24) Jyoti A, Sharma D. Neuroprotective role of Bacopa monnieri extract against aluminum-induced oxidative stress in the hippocampus of rat brain. *Neurotoxicology* 2006; 27(4): 451-457.
- 25) Murphy TH, Miyamoto M, Sastre A, Schnaar RL, Coyle JT. Glutamate toxicity in a neuronal cell line involves inhibition of cystine transport leading to oxidative stress. *Neuron* 1989; 2(6): 1547-1558.
- 26) Krutika J, Swagata T, Kalpesh P, Praveen K, Nishteswar, K. Studies of Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera* Dunal). *Int J Pharm Biol Arch* 2016; 7: 1-11.
- 27) Khanna PK, Kumar A, Ahuja A, Kaul MK. Biochemical composition of roots of *Withania somnifera* (L.) dual. *Asian J Plant Sci* 2006; 5: 1061-1063.
- 28) Dasgupta A, Tso G, Wells A. Effect of Asian ginseng, Siberian ginseng and Indian Ayurvedic medicine Ashwagandha on serum digoxin measurement by Digoxin III, a new digoxin immunoassay. *J Clin Lab Anal* 2008; 22: 295-301.
- 29) Singh N, Bhalla M, de Jager P, Gilca M. An overview on Ashwagandha: A rasayana (Rejuvenator) of ayurveda. *Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med* 2011; 8: 208-213.
- 30) Baitharu I, Jain V, Deep SN, Hota KB, Hota SK, Prasad D, Ilavazhagan G. *Withania somnifera* root extract ameliorates hypobaric hypoxia induced memory impairment in rats. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2013; 145(2): 431-441.

- 31) Brahmachari G, Mondal S, Gangopadhyay A, Gorai D, Mukhopadhyay B, Saha S, Brahmachari AK. *Swertia* (Gentianaceae): Chemical and pharmacological aspects. *Chem Biodivers* 2004; 1: 1627-1651.
- 32) Hajimehdipoor H, Dijoux-Franca MG, Mariotte AM, Amanzadeh Y, Sadat-Ebrahimi SE, Ghazi-Khansari M, Mozaffarian V. Phytochemical study of *Swertia longifolia*. *DARU J Pharm Sci* 2008; 16: 245-249.
- 33) Negi JS, Singh P, Rawat B. Chemical constituents and biological importance of *swertia*: A review. *Curr Res Chem* 2011; 3: 1-15.
- 34) Dutt B, Srivastava LJ, Singh JM. *Swertia spp*: A source of bitter compounds for medicinal use. *Ancient Sci Life* 1996; 15: 226-229.
- 35) Chandra D, Kohli G, Punetha VD, Prasad K, Bisht G, Khetwal KS, Pandey HK. Phytochemical and ethnomedicinal uses of family Gentianaceae. *Curr Res Chem* 2016; 8: 1-9.
- 36) Kaushal K, Singh H, Kant A. Hydroalcoholic extract of *Swertia Chirata* and *Swertia Cordata* attenuates hypoxia-mediated memory dysfunction by improving neuronal survival in wistar rats. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res* 2019; 12(2): 356-362.
- 37) Zanelli SA, Solenski NJ, Rosenthal RE, Fiskum G. Mechanisms of Ischemic Neuroprotection by Acetyl-L-carnitine. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 2005; 1053(1): 153-161.
- 38) Scaffidi S, Racz J, Hazelton J, McKenna MC, Fiskum G. Neuroprotection by acetyl-L-carnitine after traumatic injury to the immature rat brain. *Dev Neurosci* 2010; 32(5-6): 480-487.
- 39) Barhwal K, Singh SB, Hota SK, Jayalakshmi K, Ilavazhagan G. Acetyl-L-carnitine ameliorates hypobaric hypoxic impairment and spatial memory deficits in rats. *Eur J Pharmacol* 2007; 570(1): 97-107.
- 40) Bagetta V, Barone I, Ghiglieri V, Di Filippo M, Sgobio C, Bernardi G, Calabresi P, Picconi B. Acetyl-L-carnitine selectively prevents post-ischemic LTP via a possible action on mitochondrial energy metabolism. *Neuropharmacology* 2008; 55(2): 223-229.
- 41) Barhwal K, Hota SK, Prasad D, Singh SB, Ilavazhagan G. Hypoxia-induced deactivation of NGF-mediated ERK1/2 signaling in hippocampal cells: Neuroprotection by acetyl-L-carnitine. *J Neurosci Res* 2008; 86(12): 2705-2721.
- 42) Barhwal K, Hota S, Jain V, Prasad D, Singh S, Ilavazhagan G. Acetyl-L-carnitine (ALCAR) prevents hypobaric hypoxia-induced spatial memory impairment through extracellular related kinase-mediated nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 phosphorylation. *Neuroscience* 2009; 161(2): 501-514.
- 43) Campbell CA, Mackay KB, Patel S, King PD, Stretton JL, Hadingham SJ, Hamilton TC. Effects of isradipine, an L-type calcium channel blocker on permanent and transient focal cerebral ischemia in spontaneously hypertensive rats. *Exp Neurol* 1997; 148(1): 45-50.
- 44) Ilijic E, Guzman J, Surmeier D. The L-type channel antagonist isradipine is neuroprotective in a mouse model of Parkinson's disease. *Neurobiol Dis* 2011; 43(2): 364-371.
- 45) Barhwal K, Hota SK, Baitharu I, Prasad D, Singh SB, Ilavazhagan G. Isradipine antagonizes hypobaric hypoxia induced CA1 damage and memory impairment: complementary roles of L-type calcium channel and NMDA receptors. *Neurobiol Dis* 2009; 34(2): 230-244.
- 46) Qaid E, Zakaria R, Sulaiman S, Yusof NM, Shafin N, Othman Z, Ahmad A, Aziz CBA. Insight into potential mechanisms of hypobaric hypoxia-induced learning and memory deficit-Lessons from rat studies. *Hum Exp Toxicol* 2017; 36(12): 1315-1325.
- 47) Dai Y, Li W, Zhong M, Chen J, Liu Y, Cheng Q, Li T. Preconditioning and post-treatment with cobalt chloride in rat model of perinatal hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy. *Brain and Dev* 2014; 36(3): 228-240.
- 48) Shrivastava K, Shukla D, Bansal A, Sairam M, Banerjee P, Ilavazhagan G. Neuroprotective effect of cobalt chloride on hypobaric hypoxia-induced oxidative stress. *Neurochem Int* 2008; 52(3): 368-375.
- 49) Kelly GS. Clinical applications of N-acetylcysteine. *Altern Med Rev* 1998; 3(2): 114-127.
- 50) Fukami G, Hashimoto K, Koike K, Okamura N, Shimizu E, Iyo M. Effect of antioxidant N-acetyl-L-cysteine on behavioral changes and neurotoxicity in rats after administration of methamphetamine. *Brain Res* 2004; 1016(1): 90-95.
- 51) Fu A-L, Dong Z-H, Sun M-J. Protective effect of N-acetyl-L-cysteine on amyloid β -peptide-induced learning and memory deficits in mice. *Brain Res* 2006; 1109(1): 201-206.
- 52) Kamboj SS, Chopra K, Sandhir R. Neuroprotective effect of N-acetylcysteine in the development of diabetic encephalopathy in streptozotocin-induced diabetes. *Metab Brain Dis* 2008; 23(4): 427.
- 53) Jayalakshmi K, Sairam M, Singh S, Sharma S, Ilavazhagan G, Banerjee P. Neuroprotective effect of N-acetyl cysteine on hypoxia-induced oxidative stress in primary hippocampal culture. *Brain Res* 2005; 1046(1): 97-104.
- 54) Baluchnejadmojarad T, Roghani M. Effect of naringenin on intracerebroventricular streptozotocin-induced cognitive deficits in rat: a behavioral analysis. *Pharmacology* 2006; 78(4): 193-197.
- 55) Raza S, Khan M, Ahmad A, Ashafaq M, Islam F, Wagner A, Safhi M. Neuroprotective effect of naringenin is mediated through suppression of NF- κ B signaling pathway in experimental stroke. *Neuroscience* 2013; 230: 157-171.
- 56) Bai X, Zhang X, Chen L, Zhang J, Zhang L, Zhao X, Zhao T, Zhao Y. Protective effect of naringenin in experimental ischemic stroke: down-regulated NOD2, RIP2, NF- κ B, MMP-9 and up-regulated claudin-5 expression. *Neurochem Res* 2014; 39(8): 1405-1415.
- 57) Sarkar A, Angeline MS, Anand K, Ambasta RK, Kumar P. Naringenin and quercetin reverse the effect of hypobaric hypoxia and elicit neuroprotective response in the murine model. *Brain Res* 2012; 1481: 59-70.
- 58) Pu F, Mishima K, Irie K, Motohashi K, Tanaka Y, Orito K, Egawa T, Kitamura Y, Egashira N, Iwasaki K. Neuroprotective effects of quercetin and rutin on spatial memory impairment in an 8-arm radial maze task and neuronal death induced by repeated cerebral ischemia in rats. *J Pharmacol Sci* 2007; 104(4): 329-334.
- 59) Jembrek MJ, Vuković L, Puhović J, Erhardt J, Oršolić N. Neuroprotective effect of quercetin against hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative injury in P19 neurons. *J Mol Neurosci* 2012; 47(2): 286-299.
- 60) Patir H, Sarada S, Singh S, Mathew T, Singh B, Bansal A. Quercetin as a prophylactic measure against high altitude cerebral edema. *Free Radic Biol Med* 2012; 53(4): 659-668.
- 61) Prasad J, Baitharu I, Sharma AK, Dutta R, Prasad D, Singh SB. Quercetin reverses hypobaric hypoxia-induced hippocampal neurodegeneration and improves memory function in the rat. *High Alt Med Biol* 2013; 14(4): 383-394.
- 62) Zhou J, Zhou S, Gao Y, Zeng S. Modulatory effects of quercetin on hypobaric hypoxic rats. *Eur J Pharmacol* 2012; 674(2): 450-454.
- 63) Udayabanu M, Kumaran D, Katyal A. Free chelatable zinc modulates the cholinergic function during hypobaric hypoxia-induced neuronal damage: an in vivo study. *Neuroscience* 2012; 202: 434-445.
- 64) Trombley P, Horning M, Blakemore L. Interactions between carnosine and zinc and copper: implications for neuromodulation and neuroprotection. *Biochemistry (Mosc)* 2000; 65(7): 807-816.
- 65) Hellmich HL, Frederickson CJ, DeWitt DS, Saban R, Parsley MO, Stephenson R, Velasco M, Uchida T, Shimamura M, Prough DS. Protective effects of zinc chelation in traumatic brain injury correlate with upregulation of neuroprotective genes in rat brain. *Neurosci Lett* 2004; 355(3): 221-225.
- 66) Malairaman U, Dandapani K, Katyal A. Effect of CaEDTA on zinc mediated inflammation and neuronal apoptosis in hippocampus of an in vivo mouse model of hypobaric hypoxia. *PLoS One* 2014a; 9(10): e110253.